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Biographies/Biography:

Stelios Tsangarides' interests lie in astrophysics, education and sustainability. After his BSc at Michigan State University (US), he received a PhD in astrophysics at the Open University (UK). Since 2005, he has taught Physics at a private high-school in Cyprus, and has lead its Physics department since 2010. He cofounded Adelve Research, Innovation, Consulting & Trade to pursue his interests.

Title:

Astrotourism in Cyprus: Review of the "inaugural act"

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List of Tables and/or Info Boxes + Captions:

1 Table

Caption: Table 1. Dates and observation sites for the four pilot AstroParks and AstroCamps.

Summary:

At the end of the aptly-named AstroTourism project in Cyprus (INTEGRATED/0918/0038), this paper reviews the entertainment- and education-oriented astronomy products developed as part of an environmentally-friendly, sustainable-tourism project that centers on astronomy. Its climate has situated Cyprus in the "sun-and-sea" model of tourism for the past several decades. Recently, a critical mass of astronomers, environmental experts and tourism professionals has spearheaded a drive for an obvious, yet undeveloped, alternative: showing visitors the beauty of the Cyprus night sky, while learning about astronomy and space exploration. This AstroTourism project developed three main types of astronomy products: year-round observational material for various pristine sites on the island (based on first-time,

systematic, dark-sky measurements), astronomy-related STEAM activities and solar observations, and fact-dependent, AR/VR products. These were tested and streamlined over the course of two years in mobile venues dubbed AstroParks (single-night, family experience), AstroCamps (multiple-night camps for children and teenagers), and AstroVillages (single-night visits for skilled astronomers, with the guidance of expert Cypriot astronomer-guides). The consortium is currently in the process of seeking dark-sky accreditation for a region of the Paphos Forest, in which the background measurements of various locations have indicated such quality.

Body Text:

Introduction

Although temporarily disrupted by the CoViD-19 pandemic, tourism is rebounding, and close to reaching its pre-2020 revenue of trillions of USD, contributing a few percent of the global GDP (e.g. United Nations World Tourism Organization, 2023; Statista Research Department, 2023). In the past several decades, multiple special-interest fields have emerged, e.g., sports, culinary, religious, agrotourism, cultural and health tourism. Some of these sustainable fields provide significant benefits to local economies, both in revenue as well as in non-seasonality and egalitarian professional practices. The term astrotourism has been coined to refer to the specific sector, in which tourists undertake activities that involve the exploration of the (night) sky for at least part of their leisure time.

Despite its investment in tourism, the Republic of Cyprus is only just emerging in specialized sectors, having focused on the "sun-and-sea" model for several decades. Over the last several years, there has been a strategic drive to explore various fields of special-interest tourism (Deputy Ministry of Tourism, 2022). This work reviews a project by a group of astronomers, education, tourism, business and ICT professionals from private enterprises and academic/research institutes, to establish the first astrotourism experience on the island.

Country profile: Cyprus

The island of Cyprus is located at the easternmost corner of the Mediterranean Sea, around 35° north and 33° east. The climate comprises hot, dry summers and warm, often dry winters (Cyprus Meteorological Service, n.d.). There is no formal, government-run program measuring the hours of clear skies, but a private effort at the (new) Prodromos Observatory has been measuring this since 1 April 2023. In the past 8 months, their readings have yielded over 200 (~80%) clear or partly clear nights in a total of 244 (A. Elia, 2023, private communication). Of course, with winter (which is the rainy season) just beginning and an exceptionally clear year so far, sampling over a number of years is necessary to avoid declaring a biased figure.

Nevertheless, these conditions favor both tourism and astronomy. The former has been developed since the 1970s, with the implemented "sun-and-sea" model favoring leisure and activities related to the plentiful beachside venues on the island (Deputy Ministry of Tourism, 2022). The Republic of Cyprus has rebounded almost entirely from the pandemic, recording ~3.7 million international visitors in 2023 (compared to ~4.0 million in 2019) (Cyprus Statistical Service, 2021).

Astronomy, on the other hand, has been underdeveloped. In higher education, only a limited number of elective courses are offered in astrophysics at the University of Cyprus, and the private European University features a computational-research group in the field (Astrophysics and High-Performance Computing). Astrophysics is not part of the taught curriculum of secondary education either, having been eliminated more than a decade ago.

With the aid of a few amateur astronomers, a number of (mainly private) interests have begun the effort to establish it. In recent years, 2 observatories and a planetarium have been constructed via private funding, and an observatory through national funding. These have been equipped with large commercial telescopes and inducted in various sky-monitoring activities (A. Elia, 2023, private communication). The project reported in this work constitutes an additional effort to showcase the beauty of the Cyprus sky for tourists of various backgrounds (from casually interested guests to experienced astronomers).

The AstroTourism experience: research and development

Since its inception, the AstroTourism project has been focused on providing an entertaining and educational astronomy experience, while conforming to the principles of sustainable and responsible tourism. A broad spectrum of products have been designed for the duration of at least one and possibly several nights:

- *Observational products:*

The observational experience comprised 3 activities: an unaided-eye uranography, a number of targets for binoculars and another set for commercial telescopes. The aim was to entertain as well as educate the guests, both in astronomy as well as its cultural, historical, even mythical influences. To aid guests, star maps (adapted to be read in low, red light) were provided at the beginning of each night and the principles of astrophotography were highlighted during observations. Furthermore, a solar telescope was set up for day observations.

To facilitate all three styles of observation from anywhere in Cyprus and at any time, a database comprising most of the constellations observable on the island was prepared, and a number of targets of scientific, cultural and/or historical importance were

highlighted in each. An expert astronomer guide (AstroGuide - the person who will be leading the visitor groups after commercialization) will be able to use the database to prepare target lists. Also, a curriculum for training the AstroGuides was developed using the principles of STEAM education.

In an effort to provide high-quality observations, we determined the darkest sites on the island. Illumination maps uncovered the most promising locations. At each of these, measurements of the magnitude of the dark background were taken with a (commercial) Sky Quality Meter, on a fixed grid of angles along the entire sky dome, throughout the duration of multiple nights. The methodology was published in detail elsewhere (Elia & Tryfon, 2022). Despite the proximity of a number of medium-sized cities, the readings ranged in magnitude from 21.20 to 21.74, which are promising enough to use in applying for dark-sky accreditation of a large region of the Paphos Forest (in which these locations are found) at various international organizations (DarkSky International [formerly International Dark-Sky Association], Starlight Foundation).

- *STEAM activities:*

In order to supply a pedagogic and entertaining daytime experience, 15 STEAM activities were designed and incorporated in a database, intended to be used on the campsite. These activities are designed to foster creativity and critical thinking while integrating astronomy, literacy and digital skills and prioritizing sustainability. This outdoor-based learning promotes a connection to astronomy and environmental conservation, encouraging responsible behaviors and fostering an environmentally conscious generation. For the purposes of delivering the activities to an audience of varied age, an additional STEAM curriculum was created to train the STEAM educators that would accompany the visitor groups.

- *Immersive experiences:*

A virtual-reality and an augmented-reality product were developed, primarily to educate guests on aspects of space exploration that are difficult to grasp due to lack of direct experience, and also to provide an additional thrill. The VR product features a factual adventure inspired by the NASA effort to explore the Mars Jezero crater. The AR product constitutes a hike through a nature trail, scaled to the solar system itself. The start of the hike symbolizes the location of the sun, with a marker providing information on it. Markers are subsequently found at appropriate scaled distances for each planet, providing interesting facts about them. Both products relate a fictional character's story simultaneously with scientific knowledge, and were prepared with the expert consultation of an entertainment professional.

- *Environmental orientation:*

Environmental experts prepared a number of documents to reduce environmental impact and support local communities. These included orientation and best-practices guidelines for the campsites, highlighting natural sights while focusing on health and safety. In addition, environmental benchmarking guidelines, such as a “Zero Kilometre Food” document, were prepared to shape future sustainable astrotourism efforts. These were included in the training syllabus of the AstroGuides. Finally, the camp gear was specifically selected for its minimum environmental impact.

Implementation and evaluation

The AstroTourism experience was designed for guests to stay in campsites near the observation locations, with every meal cooked specifically and served at camp. This enabled the set-up to remain comprehensive yet mobile, so as to sample multiple sites and products.

Four pilot sessions were conducted in 1.5 years, providing 3 distinct experiences: AstroParks, AstroCamps and AstroVillages. The first included a single-night stay, in which guests experienced the observational part, and as many of the other products as they wished. AstroCamps hosted visitors aged 7-18 years (parental consent was secured) for 2 nights, and featured all the products. In the third venue, expert amateur astronomers were welcomed in (Astro)Villages near selected observation sites, and provided equipment and guidance to conduct their own observations over 1 night. Table 1 shows the dates and locations of the pilot sessions for the AstroParks and AstroCamps.

Table 1. Dates and observation sites for the pilot AstroParks and AstroCamps.

Session	Date	Site
1	2022 March 25 - April 02	Machairas Forest
2	2022 July 26 - August 3	Paphos Forest
3	2023 April 20-25	Amiantos Star Park
4	2023 September 12-18	Amiantos Star Park

The experience was free, and guests evaluated its different aspects. Questionnaires for all products were prepared, with guests rating each aspect from 1 (poor) to 5 (excellent). Across all pilots, guests evaluated the observational, STEAM and immersive products close to perfect, with their average scores exceeding 4. The campsite organization scored a bit lower, but still averaged > 3.

Conclusions

The Cypriot inaugural astrotourism program developed a unique range of astronomy-related experiences, including observations, STEAM activities

and immersive products. In addition, the background of the Cyprus night sky was measured and dark-sky accreditation will be sought for a section of the Paphos Forest. Tested across 4 pilot sessions, the full experience scored high in guest evaluation, clearly meriting commercialization, under the fundamental project guidelines of sustainable, educational and entertaining tourism.

References:

Cyprus Meteorological Service. (2020). Retrieved December 21 2023, from https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/dm/dm.nsf/home_en/home_en?openform

Cyprus Statistical Service. (2021). Tourism. Retrieved December 21 2023, from <https://www.cystat.gov.cy/en/SubthemeStatistics?id=51>

Deputy Ministry of Tourism. (2022). Strategic Planning. Retrieved December 21 2023, from https://www.tourism.gov.cy/tourism/tourism.nsf/planning_en/planning_en?OpenDocument

Elia, A. & Tryfon, S. (2022). Evaluation of the Cypriot Night Sky. Paper presented at the 12th Hellenic Conference of Amateur Astronomy. University of Patras.

Statista Research Department. (2023). Global tourism industry - statistics & facts. Retrieved December 21 2023, from <https://www.statista.com/topics/962/global-tourism/#topicOverview>

United Nations World Tourism Organization. (2023). Tourism on track for full recovery as new data shows strong start to 2023. Retrieved December 21 2023, from <https://www.unwto.org/news/tourism-on-track-for-full-recovery-as-new-data-shows-strong-start-to-2023>

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